

THE PRAGMATIC ASPECT OF EXPRESSIVENESS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH NEWSPAPER HEADLINES

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Abstract:

This article investigates the pragmatic aspect of expressiveness in English and Uzbek newspaper headlines. It involves how expressive means and stylistic devices influence the emotions, interpretations of text. The qualitative comparative approach is used, and the headlines are analyzed in terms of speech acts, implicitness, emotiveness and evaluative words.

Key words:

Expressiveness, pragmatics, media discourse, newspaper headlines, evaluative vocabulary, expressive means, implicitness;

In the past, information in the newspapers in Uzbekistan or elsewhere was almost completely factual, neutral that aims to transmit news to the readers without expecting much, rather than now that newspapers' functions are more than what it was before: influencing the readers, exert emotional impact, shaping the public opinion. Likely headlines of newspapers were also descriptive that lacked pragmatic impact however the digital media entered the industry with updates such as expressive headlines, pragmatic styles, emotive and evaluative vocabulary usage. Moreover in that process headlines are not merely summary of information but plays an important role to grab attention, guide the audiences' view. "newspaper headlines are persuasive rather than informative" [Ifantidou. E, 2009:41]. In other words, headlines are designed to attract the readers and the expressiveness is mainly used in headlines in this regard.

The category of expressiveness is studied from different aspects by scholars such as Ch.L.Bally I.V.Arnold, D.U.Ashurova, I.R. Galperin, Q. Musayev include it into a Stylistics. While many other scientists like J. R.Searle, G. N.Leech, T.A.van Dijk, V.N.Teliya include expressiveness into pragmatic category. "expressiveness may be understood as a kind of intensification of an utterance or of a part of it depending on the position in the utterance of the means that manifest this category and what these means are." [Galperin.R.I, 1977:26]

In other words, expressiveness is the way of making the sentence or part of it emotional and strong. It heavily relies on what words are chosen and where they come in a sentence. Galperin argues that emotiveness is not expressiveness but integral part of it. And the language units are used to create the logical and emotional intensification of the utterance. These language units are called expressive means. Moreover, stylistic devices are also employed in a text to create expressiveness, emerge in the context. Words get a connotative meaning. I.V.Arnold claims expressiveness as "a property of a text or part of a text, intensify meaning results the emotional and empathetic impact" [Arnold.V.I, 2002:99]

In addition, Geoffrey N. Leech (1983) emphasizes the pragmatic aspect of expressiveness that he explains that it conveys emotions like approval, disapproval, irony or emphasis, Expressiveness is not just an intensification but revealing the writer or speakers' subjective evaluations.

The headline of newspapers are not merely a decoration but the pragmatic tool to manipulate reader's opinions and urge them to be their life long consumer. However not always

pragmatic aim is explicit but requires an inference (logic and conclusion) to find the expressiveness, implicit meaning behind headlines.

By several scholars investigates precisely the phenomenon of expressiveness how it reflects culture, customs of communities.

"Customs,cultural codes and traditions are depicted in Newspapers, in order to understand how one nation's cultural and social life, it is substantial to analyze the phenomenon of expressiveness " [M.D.Teshabayeva et.al, 2025:145]

The qualitative comparative approach is used to investigate the pragmatic aspect of expressiveness in newspaper headlines. The data are collected from The Guardian (English newspaper) and Vatanparvar (Uzbek newspaper) which are published in 2026. This investigation is based on more than 30 headlines, 15 for each newspaper. The selection is based on : presence of expressiveness and evaluative words, socio-political relevance ;

In this article 3 headlines from each newspaper, overall 6 are discussed in detail. However result of the research relies on the much broader corpus. Each headline is examined in the terms of speech acts, implicitness and expressiveness. A comparative approach is used to identify differences and similarities of pragmatic aspect of expressiveness in newspaper headlines in two languages, English and Uzbek.

– In guardian, " PM ousts top civil servant in shake - up of No 10 team"

In that sentence : expressiveness is realized with the help of expressive means which are lexical : The emotive verb "oust" is used instead of "replace" that shows the severeness of the conflict ; syntactical : ellipsis - the abundance of the articles before PM and top servant as it shows the urgency of a news ;

along with stylistic devices : metaphor " shake up" is physical action of shaking an object here used to describe the changes in the government; metonymy " No 10 team" by referring the residence of Britain's prime minister, the whole government (people) is described ; evaluative adjective top is used to refer to the civil servant that shows how important of this person's status.

By selecting these words, writer grabs the attention of readers and make negative evaluations cause doubt about the stability of the government.

– In Vatanparvar, "Birlashgan o'zar, birlashmagan to'zar."

The news about mahalla's place in individual's life , Uzbek proverb is chosen to give the implicit evaluation to the text, urges the reader to create the national unity, solidarity and harmony in their community and implicitly refer to Unity – positive(growth) ; Not unity – negative(destruction) evaluations ; Antithesis is caused by opposing o'zar, to'zar, birlashgan, birlashmagan that activates the readers emotions.Compare to Guardian, Vatanparvar selects the headlines more implicit and culturally embedded in order to shape the public attitude .

– "Toma-toma ko'l bo'lar".

Another uzbek proverb partly used which is popular among the Uzbek people, makes it much easier to be understood by reader's of a newspaper. The proverb itself : "Toma-toma ko'l bo'lar, Tiyinlardan so'm bo'lar " Or English equivalent "Little and often fills the purse" has a positive meaning, however in the context it emphasizes completely negative news which is about stealing small amount of money from patient's payment voucher and it will led to cumulative gain. Pragmatic aim is realized with the repetitions : toma-toma, contrast : opposing

the width of drops (tomchi) and lake (ko'l) to warn the reader's to be cautious and do not let small things go unnoticed.

- "January blues? Longing for an escape to the sun? Perfect timing for criminals to cash in"

This is the headline for the newspaper Guardian and it concerns with almost same matter like Vatanparvar but different expressive means are used to influence on the readers. Rhetorical questions are used to connect emotionally with the readers and warn them upcoming danger, scamming. The headline is more direct, immediate awareness is promoted, however in the headline above "Little and often fills the purse" is more indirect and culturally embedded.

- "Vatan dardi bilan yongan millatmiz"

Order of the words in the headline shows speaker's intention is to exert emotional impact, not "Millatimiz vatan dardi bilan yongan" but exact structure of a sentence urges the readers to feel the national pride. In addition, culturally emotive words like millatimiz, dard raise the expressiveness of a sentence. The usage of metaphore "yongan millat" creates the visual picture in the eyes of the readers and dramatizes the event.

- "Streets are full of blood" Inside Iran's anti regime protests.

Powerful metaphor "Streets are full of blood" dramatizes the situation and shows extreme violence and catastrophic loss. The word "blood" is highly emotive in many contexts. Sentence evokes horror, concern among people and alert, indirectly urge them to protest against such morally and socially significant tragedy.

In conclusion this research investigates the pragmatic aspect of expressiveness in headlines of newspapers and what linguistic devices intensify meaning and influence the readers. In the analysis, expressive means, stylistic devices: metaphors, irony, emotive words, repetition, rhetorical questions, antithesis are revealed to show the communicative aim of the author and guide the readers' perception. The comparative analysis shows that expressiveness in both newspapers is utilized to pursued, warn, evaluate. There are differences in stylistic choices, or degree of intensity of a meaning as Uzbek newspaper headlines promotes community values, solidarity while English headlines are more individualized and dramatized. Thus, the expressiveness in headlines is the essential pragmatic tool to influence the public opinion, reflect language and culture.

References:

1. Galperin.R.I. STYLISTICS. –HIGHER SCHOOL, 1977.– 26
2. Ifantidou.E. Newspaper headlines and relevance: Ad hoc concepts in ad hoc contexts.– Journal of Pragmatics, 2009. – 41.
3. Khusanova.Z.A. Cross-National pragmatic patterns in Mass Media Language: Evidence from American And Uzbek Newspapers.–American journal of philological sciences, 2025.P. 21–24.
4. Leech.N.G. Principles of Pragmatics. –Longman London and New York.1983
5. Musayev.Q. English stylistics. –Adolat. 2003.
6. Navruzova.N.Kh. The role of expressiveness as a connotative component in the semantic structure of the word. American journal of education and learning, 2025 –Vol.3, No. 3.–P. 288–293.
7. Safarmakhmatova.N.Z. Expressive Tendencies of Language in the World of Print Media.– European science methodological journal, 2023 – Vol. 1, No. 3. – P. 38-40.

8. Teshabayeva D.M,Zulpukarov.Z.K,Sabiraliyeva.M.Z. The issue of cultural code in expressive means of newspaper and publicistic style. –The lingua Spectrum,2025. P.138–148.
9. Арнольд, И.В. Стилистика современного английского языка / И.В. Арнольд. – М.: Просвещение, 2002, С. 99.